

Mini-review

Cow Calf Contact (CCC) in dairy production

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CARE4DAIRY

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1. The issue

Across Europe standard dairy production has, for decades, relied on separation of the calf from the cow, often within a few hours or days, to maximise the amount of milk available to humans. This is contrary to the natural calf rearing behaviour of cattle, where social and nutritional weaning would typically occur after around 6-9 months (Weary et al., 2008). Early separation has an overall negative impact on the welfare of cows and calves (Meagher et al., 2019) and is an important concern of European citizens about dairy farming (Cardoso et al., 2017). Changing systems to avoid early separation is considered an important novel dairy sustainability practice to European citizens (Naspetti, et al., 2021).

2. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

Two systematic reviews on prolonged cow calf contact were published in 2019, one focussing on the dairy cow and calf health (Beaver et al., 2019) and the other on behaviour, welfare and productivity (Meagher et al., 2019). The literature on prolonged cow calf contact is not yet well developed, but is growing.

2.1. Calf and cow performances

Mother-reared calves have better overall growth (two reviews: Costa, et al., 2016; Johnsen et al., 2016) before weaning, likely due to a higher ingestion of milk (Nicolao et al., 2022). However, saleable milk is reduced when calves suckle their dam, but these reductions may not continue beyond weaning (Meagher et al., 2019).

2.2. Calf behaviour

Calves reared with cows develop fewer behaviours indicative of poor welfare, including tongue rolling and cross sucking (Froberg et al., 2008; Froberg & Lidfors, 2009; Roth et al., 2009). Cow rearing calves support the development of calf social skills (Flower & Weary, 2001; Vaarst et al., 2001; Wagner et al., 2012; Santo et al., 2020), social competence (Waiblinger et al., 2020a,b) and increased locomotor play (Waiblinger et al., 2020a). Cognitive abilities (as measured in a maze test) after weaning are higher in calves raised by the dam or foster cow compared to isolated calves (Broucek et al., 2020).

At weaning, mother-reared calves can show a pessimistic judgement bias indicative of poor mood (Daros et al., 2014) and lower weight gain (Roth et al., 2009; Veissier et al., 2013). The negative effects of social and nutritional weaning on the calves' vocalisation rate and behaviour can be mitigated with fence-line contact during weaning (Price et al.,

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years, assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

2003) and by separating the cow and calf part of the day before weaning (restricted contact: Froberg et al., 2008; Roth et al., 2009; half day contact: Veissier et al., 2013). Negative effects on growth of weaning cow-reared calves are usually mitigated by the increased growth preweaning (Meagher et al., 2019; Valnickova et al., 2015).

2.3. Calf health

There is mixed evidence for the effect of prolonged cow calf contact on some aspects of calf health such as cryptosporidiosis, pneumonia, immunity and mortality. However, variations in impacts observed on calves' health seem to be due to variations in disease prevalence on the farm and immunity transfer by the colostrum (Johnsen et al. 2016; Beaver et al., 2019). In utero transfer of protective immunity is weak in calves, making them sensitive to environmental pathogens (Godden et al., 2019; Cardoso et al., 2021) and making mandatory the absorption of maternal colostrum in the very first hours after birth (Godden et al., 2019). Early separation from the dam is often presented as a way to protect them from diseases (Faubert & Litvinsky, 2000, Muskens et al., 2003; Dauschies & Najdrowskii, 2005; McGuirk, 2008), sometimes without scientific evidence (Beaver et al., 2019). It allows farmers to control and guarantee the quality and quantity of the colostrum provided to calves, improving the transfer of maternal immunoglobulins to the calf. Despite previous suggestions to the contrary, cow calf contact is not a significant risk factor for paratuberculosis and when colostrum provision and hygiene of maternity pens are good, rearing the calf with its dam has no effect on calf health and can even limit scours (Beaver et al., 2019).

2.4. Cow behaviour and health

Cows bond to their calves over 24-72 h post-calving (through placentophagia, licking, and proximity) and the bond continues to strengthen for some weeks (von Keyserlingk, Weary 2007). Dairy cows choose to spend time with their calves, allowing them to suckle when that is available in a free-choice system (Johnsen et al., 2021). Demonstration of the strength of the cow-calf bond is evident at sudden separation from the calf with some cows displaying pronounced behavioural signs such as vocalisations and agitation up to 7 days (Veissier et al., 2013), which may be mitigated using gradual weaning methods (gradual decrease of milk intake and gradual decrease of cow-calf contact, see Whalin et al., 2021 for a review). Social skills developed during dam-rearing better prepare cows for life in the herd. For example, heifers that have been allowed to suckle their dam tend to show more submissive and non-confrontational postures than heifers that have been reared on an automatic milk feeder without contact with adult cows (Wagner et al., 2012). Dam reared calves show more exploratory behaviour (Kalber & Barth, 2014) and are more active than calves reared on an automatic milk feeder without contact with adult cows (Wagner et al., 2013).

Allowing calves to suckle for a prolonged period has been shown in a number of studies to be protective against mastitis for cows (reviewed in Beaver et al., 2019), potentially due to the calf drinking residual milk that is not collected by machine (de Passille et al.,

2008). Fertility indicators are improved in dairy cows rearing calves, which may also improve cow longevity (Johnsen et al., 2016). Meagher et al. (2019) reviewing the literature reported that 'allowing cows to nurse calves generally decreased the volume of milk available for sale during the nursing period, but we found no consistent evidence of reduced milk production over a longer period'.

3. Summary

Prolonged cow calf contact (CCC)

- Promotes cow health, has no negative impact on calf health and improves overall welfare,
- Benefits to the development of social skills, especially in female, with impacts still visible in adulthood,
- Improves calf growth,
- Reduces the amount of saleable milk. This effect may not continue beyond weaning.

Nutritional and social weaning by abrupt separation between calf and dam

- Results in a transient reduction of calf growth, that can be compensated by a higher growth prior to weaning compared to calves not reared with their dam,
- Is stressful for both cow and calf. The stress can be mitigated by gradual weaning.

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